

Mechanochemical synthesis of highly dispersed Cu on CeO₂ for the reverse water-gas shift reaction

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ABSTRACT

Copper-based catalysts are highly promising for carbon dioxide (CO₂) reduction to carbon monoxide (CO) via the reverse water-gas shift (RWGS) reaction, owing to their efficiency, copper abundance, sustainability and cost-effectiveness. However, enhancing CO₂ conversion and CO selectivity requires achieving high copper dispersion through a scalable and economical synthesis method. In this study, Cu was combined with CeO₂ rods via a mechanochemical ball-milling approach to optimize performance in the RWGS reaction. Comprehensive characterization and kinetic analysis revealed how metal content influences catalyst architecture and activity. Additionally, in situ diffuse reflectance infrared Fourier transform spectroscopy was used to investigate the nature of copper species at different dispersion levels and elucidate the reaction pathway. Notably, the Cu/CeO₂ catalyst with a high Cu loading (~5 wt%) and well-dispersed active sites achieved an activity (R_{Cu}(CO₂)) of 4.8 × 10⁻⁵ mol_{CO2} m_{Cu}⁻² s⁻¹ with over 99% CO selectivity at 450 °C. These findings provide a robust strategy for developing high-performance Cu-based catalysts for the RWGS reaction.

1. Introduction

Converting CO₂, a major greenhouse gas, into high-added-value products at an industrial scale using H₂ from renewable sources offers a promising and sustainable approach for CO₂ chemical recycling, supporting the goal of net-zero carbon emissions across various industrial processes. [1–6] Among various CO₂ transformation pathways, the reverse water-gas shift (RWGS) reaction (Eq. (1)) stands out as a particularly advantageous method for producing CO, a key feedstock for downstream Fischer-Tropsch (F-T) synthesis of long-chain hydrocarbons or methanol. [7–10] Moreover, CO plays a critical role as an industrial feedstock in the synthesis of high-value chemicals and fuels. [11,12]

In the RWGS reaction, high temperatures are typically required to achieve sufficient CO₂ conversion based on the primary reaction (Eq. (1)). However, at these elevated temperatures, a competing side reaction can occur, reducing CO selectivity by favoring the hydrogenation of CO₂ to methane (Eq. (2)).

Noble metal catalysts, such as Pd-, Pt-, Ru-, and Rh-based systems, have been extensively developed for this reaction due to their high activity and stability. [13–16] However, their practical application is limited by high costs and suboptimal performance. To address these challenges, significant efforts have been directed toward developing non-noble metal catalysts, including Cu-, Mo-, Ni-, Co-, and Fe-based systems, which offer high activity, selectivity, and, most importantly, lower cost. [17–21] Among these, Cu-based catalysts stand out as ideal candidates due to their high CO selectivity over CH₄, moderate

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operating temperatures, and strong resistance to carbon deposition. Furthermore, Cu-based catalysts benefit from synergistic interactions with supports, further enhancing their cost-effectiveness for sustainable and industrial applications. [22,23]

For example, Liu et al. achieved exceptional activity and durability for high-temperature RWGS by stabilizing copper clusters on ceria surfaces (Cu content: 15 wt%). [18] Similarly, Lu et al. demonstrated that modifying micron-sized Cu powder with CeO₂ species (Cu content: 40 wt %) derived from different cerium precursor salts enhanced CO₂ conversion, with a dense CeO₂ shell forming during H₂ pretreatment. [1] However, efficient methods for maximizing copper atom utilization through simple and rapid synthesis remain a challenge for industrial applications.

Compared with conventional co-precipitation [18,24–26] and impregnation [27–29] methods, the catalysts synthesized via mechanochemical ball milling offer distinct advantages in sustainability and defect engineering (Table S13). This solvent-free, scalable process aligns with green chemistry principles by eliminating hazardous solvents and high-temperature treatments. [30,31] The mechanical force during ball milling induces localized high-temperature spots, facilitating atomic-scale Cu dispersion, as well as the formation of abundant oxygen vacancies and Cu-O-Ce interfacial structures. [32] These modifications enhance CO₂ adsorption and activation, resulting in improved RWGS performance at lower temperatures. However, challenges remain in precisely controlling particle size, local coordination environments, and reproducibility across batches, especially for complex multi-component systems. Additionally, the high-energy input and potential contamination from milling media may affect material purity and scalability under industrial settings. [33–35] Despite these limitations, mechanochemistry continues to offer a sustainable and versatile pathway for next-generation catalyst development.

In a previous study, we found that mono- and bimetallic Co-based catalysts enhanced CH₄ and CO₂ conversion on CeO₂ surfaces in methane dry reforming. Using a mechanochemical synthesis method, we significantly improved Co dispersion on the support surface, demonstrating its potential for catalytic optimization. [36]

In the present study, we test a series of Cu-based catalysts produced from the mechanochemical reaction of a copper salt with CeO₂ nanorods and evaluate their performance in the RWGS reaction. To investigate the effects of mechanochemical synthesis, we conduct comprehensive physicochemical characterization and in situ diffuse reflectance infrared Fourier transform spectroscopy (DRIFTS) analysis to reveal the unique features introduced during the milling process, comparing these catalysts with those prepared through conventional impregnation. Additionally, we examine the influence of copper content on the RWGS mechanism in these samples.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Chemicals

Copper(II) acetate hydrate (Cu₂(CH₃COO)₄·xH₂O, 99.99%), cerium (III) nitrate hexahydrate (Ce(NO₃)₃·6H₂O, 99%), and sodium hydroxide (NaOH) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Ethanol was purchased from various sources. All chemicals and reagents were used without any further purification. Deionized (DI) water (18 MΩ·cm) was used in all experiments.

2.2. Synthesis of CeO₂ nanorods (CeO₂-R)

CeO₂ nanorods were used as a support material due to their higher density of oxygen vacancies compared to cubic and polyhedral CeO₂, as reported in previous studies. [37,38] A certain amount of Ce(NO₃)₃·6H₂O was dissolved in water with a total cationic concentration of 0.4 M and mixed with 15.4 g of sodium hydroxide dissolved in 70 mL water under vigorous stirring. The as-prepared mixed solution was

sealed in a 100 mL autoclave at 100 °C for 24 h. The obtained sample was centrifuged, washed thoroughly with deionized water and ethanol, dried at 60 °C overnight, and calcined in air at 500 °C for 4 h. The final product was named CeO₂-R.

2.3. Synthesis of Cu/CeO₂-BM catalysts

The catalysts were synthesized using a high-speed vibrating ball miller (Fritsch mini-mill Pulverisette 23). In a typical ball milling procedure, a proper amount of copper(II) acetate and the as-synthesized CeO₂ nanorods were placed in a 10 mL stainless-steel vessel along with a 15 mm diameter ZrO₂ milling ball (11.57 g) to achieve a nominal Cu loading of *x* (*x* = 1, 5, 10, 15 and 25) wt%. The power-to-ball ratio was 10.7. The mixture was milled for 60 min at a vibration frequency of 50 Hz and the resulting material was calcined at 500 °C for 4 h. The catalysts were named *x*CuCe-BM. To investigate the effect of milling parameters on RWGS, a series of experiments were conducted by varying the vibration frequency (15 and 50 Hz) and milling time (10 and 60 min). In each experiment, only one parameter was altered, while all others were kept constant. No Fe, Ni, or Zr was detected in the ball-milled samples by inductively coupled plasma-optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES) analyses.

2.4. Synthesis of 5CuCe-IWI

A CeO₂ nanorod-supported Cu catalyst with a metal loading of 5 wt% was prepared using the incipient wetness impregnation (IWI) method. The sample was calcined at 500 °C for 4 h. The catalyst was then crushed (sieve mesh 80). This sample is named as 5CuCe-IWI.

2.5. Catalyst characterization

Powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis was performed on a Bruker AXS D8 X-ray diffractometer (Cu-Kα radiation, λ = 1.5418 Å, 40 kV and 40 mA; Bruker, Germany). The scan was performed in continuous mode over a 2θ range of 10° to 90°, with a step size of 0.01° and a dwell time of 2.0 s per step. The sample was mounted on a zero-background holder and analyzed at room temperature under ambient conditions. Data acquisition and analysis were carried out using HighScore Plus software. The lattice parameter of these samples was determined by the Debye–Scherrer and Bragg equations from the (311) plane.

$$d_{hkl} = \frac{\lambda}{2\sin\theta} \quad (3)$$

$$d_{hkl} = \frac{a}{\sqrt{h^2 + k^2 + l^2}} \quad (4)$$

where *a* is the lattice constant that is calculated from Eq. (4) using *d*₃₁₁ obtained from the XRD angle introduced in Eq. (3).

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images and energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDX) spectra were obtained with a Zeiss Auriga field emission SEM equipped with an Oxford EDX detector. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM), high-resolution TEM (HRTEM), and high-angle annular dark field scanning TEM (HAADF-STEM) images were acquired with a double Aberration Corrected and Monochromated Thermo Fisher Spectra 300 microscope operated at 200 kV and equipped with a SuperX EDX detector.

ICP-OES was conducted on a 5100 ICP-OES from Agilent Technologies. 20 mg of catalyst was dissolved in a mixture of concentrated acids (10 mL HNO₃ + 4 mL HF) under microwave for complete dissolution of CeO₂-supported Cu. The HF in the digest was then neutralized with boric acid, filtered and diluted to a suitable concentration for ICP analysis.

The specific surface area was analyzed on a Micromeritics TriStar II 3020 and calculated by the Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) method. 100 mg of the sample was pretreated at 250 °C for 2 h to remove adsorbed water and contaminants.

The Cu dispersion (D_{Cu}) and exposed surface area (S_{Cu}) were determined by N_2O titration on a Micromeritics AutoChem II 2920 instrument. Initially, 100 mg of calcined sample was reduced at 600 °C in a 5% H_2/Ar mixture (30 mL min^{-1}) for 1 h, with H_2 consumption accounted as A_1 . Subsequently, upon cooling to 60 °C, the sample was exposed to N_2O (30 mL min^{-1}) for 1 h to ensure thorough oxidation of surface metallic copper to Cu_2O . Finally, calibrated hydrogen (5 vol% H_2/Ar) pulse reduction at 350 °C was performed to quantify the quantity of surface Cu_2O species, with H_2 consumption accounted as A_2 . D_{Cu} and S_{Cu} were calculated using the following equations:

$$D_{Cu}(\%) = \frac{2 \times A_2}{A_1} \times 100 \quad (5)$$

$$S_{Cu}(\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}) = \frac{D_{Cu} \times \omega_{Cu} \times N_A \times A_{Cu}}{M_{Cu}} \quad (6)$$

where ω_{Cu} is the Cu mass fraction (%), and m_{cat} is the mass of the catalyst (g). $M_{Cu} = 63.55 \text{ g} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$. N_A represents the Avogadro's number ($6.02 \times 10^{23} \text{ mol}^{-1}$). A_{Ni} is the Cu cross-sectional area ($6.85 \times 10^{-20} \text{ m}^2/\text{atom}$).

Hydrogen temperature-programmed reduction (H_2 -TPR) was performed on a Chemstar-TPX instrument equipped with a thermal conductivity detector (TCD). Firstly, about 50 mg of catalyst were pretreated at 110 °C (10 °C min^{-1}) under Ar flow (50 mL min^{-1}) for 1 h and then cooled down to 35 °C. The TPR was performed from 35 °C to 850 °C with a constant heating speed of 10 °C min^{-1} under a flow of 10% H_2 in Ar (50 mL min^{-1}). Copper oxide (CuO , 97%) was used to calibrate the TCD signal. Temperature-programmed desorption of CO_2 (CO_2 -TPD) was conducted with an adsorption/desorption system Micromeritics AutoChem HP chemisorption Analyzer. 100 mg of sample was pretreated at 90 °C for 30 min with He. Then, the sample was cooled to 50 °C and reduced at 600 °C at a rate of 5 °C min^{-1} for 1 h under a flow of 10% H_2 in Ar. After cooling and saturating with CO_2 for 1 h, the sample was purged with He for 2 h to remove physically adsorbed CO_2 . Subsequently, the sample was heated to 800 °C with a rate of 5 °C min^{-1} .

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was conducted using a ThermoFisher K-alpha X-ray source operating at 150 eV for all-range spectra and 50 eV for fine spectrum. The charging effect was corrected by adjusting the binding energy of the C 1s (C—C) peak to 284.8 eV.

Electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) spectra were recorded on a Bruker EMXplus spectrometer at room temperature.

In situ DRIFTS was employed to record the spectra of species adsorbed on the catalyst surfaces during RWGS. The experiments were conducted using a Bruker Vertex 70 spectrometer. The reactor was specially designed to minimize dead volume. All samples were reduced at 600 °C in a 10% H_2/Ar flow (40 mL min^{-1} , 0.1 MPa) for 60 min, then cooled to 50 °C to obtain the background spectrum. The gas flow was then adjusted to an $H_2:CO_2:Ar$ ratio of 3:1:4 (40 mL min^{-1}) at the same temperature, and spectra were simultaneously collected to monitor changes in the intensity of various surface species. In all measurements, spectra were obtained by averaging 64 sequentially collected scans at a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} . The spectra were obtained in Kubelka-Munk (KM) units, which have been shown to scale linearly with adsorbate concentration. [39]

2.6. Activity tests

The catalytic performance of the catalysts was evaluated in a fixed-bed stainless steel tubular reactor with an inner diameter of 9 mm. Typically, 0.1 g of catalyst was mixed with 0.4 g silicon carbide and reduced at 600 °C for 1 h under atmospheric pressure in a 10% H_2/N_2 flow (30 mL min^{-1}) with a ramp rate of 5 °C min^{-1} . The reaction was conducted at 300–600 °C at 0.1 MPa with N_2 as internal gas and a flow-to-weight ratio (F/W) of 30,000 mL $g^{-1} h^{-1}$ with a $H_2/CO_2/N_2$ molar ratio of 69:23:8. Products were analyzed on-line with an Agilent 490 micro gas chromatograph equipped with thermal conductivity detectors

(TCD), employing three columns: Stabilwax, MS 5 Å, and Plot U.

Kinetic tests were performed in a fixed-bed reactor at 1 atm with 100 mg of catalyst diluted with SiC. The catalyst was reduced in 10% H_2/Ar at 600 °C for 1 h before the reaction. A gas mixture of $H_2:CO_2:N_2 = 69:23:8$ (total flow: 50 mL min^{-1} , GHSV = 30,000 mL $g^{-1} h^{-1}$) was used. Products were analyzed by online GC-TCD after 60 min stabilization at each temperature (350–400 °C). For the reaction order test, one of the H_2 or CO_2 concentrations was varied while the others were kept constant, and the CO_2 conversion values were kept between 5% and 20%.

The carbon balance closure (δ_C) was determined for each experiment and confirmed to be over 90% between the reactant and product streams according to the equation:

$$\delta_C = \frac{CO_{2,out} + CO_{out} + CH_{4,out}}{CO_{2,in}} \times 100\% \quad (7)$$

Conversion (X) and selectivity (S) were calculated as follows:

$$X(CO_2) = \left(1 - \frac{CO_{2,out} \times N_{2,in}}{N_{2,out} \times CO_{2,in}} \right) \times 100\% \quad (8)$$

$$S(CO) = \frac{CO_{out}}{CO_{out} + CH_{4,out}} \times 100\% \quad (9)$$

The moles of CO_2 consumed per mass of catalyst ($R_{cat}(CO_2)$) and reaction activity ($R_{Cu}(CO_2)$) based on the copper surface area was calculated as:

$$R_{cat}(CO_2)(\text{mol}_{CO_2} \cdot \text{g}^{-1} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}) = \frac{X_{CO_2} \times V_{CO_2}}{m_{cat} \times V_m \times 3600} \quad (10)$$

$$R_{Cu}(CO_2)(\text{mol}_{CO_2} \cdot \text{m}_{Cu}^{-2} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}) = \frac{X_{CO_2} \times V_{CO_2}}{m_{cat} \times \omega_{Cu} \times S_{Cu} \times V_m \times 3600} \quad (11)$$

where V_{CO_2} is the inlet volumetric flow of CO_2 (L h^{-1}). $V_m = 22.4 \text{ L} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$. m_{cat} is the mass of catalyst. ω_{Cu} is the Cu mass fraction (%). S_{Cu} is the copper surface area.

The long-time stability was evaluated in the fixed-bed stainless steel tubular reactor. After pretreatment at 600 °C for 1 h under atmospheric pressure in a 10% H_2/N_2 flow (30 mL min^{-1}) with a ramp rate of 5 °C min^{-1} , the reaction was conducted at 500 °C at 0.1 MPa and a flow-to-weight ratio (F/W) of 30,000 mL $g^{-1} h^{-1}$ with an $H_2/CO_2/N_2$ molar ratio of 69:23:8 for 80 h.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Catalytic performance

For all catalysts and temperatures tested (300–600 °C), CO was the only detected byproduct, originating from the CO_2 reduction reaction. CO_2 conversion increased with temperature, reaching near-equilibrium conditions at 500 °C and above (Fig. 1a). Notably, CO selectivity remained close to 100% across all catalysts, with no significant variations observed (Fig. 1a). For 1CuCe-BM, a lower conversion was attributed to an insufficient number of active sites due to its lower copper content, despite its high copper dispersion. The 5CuCe-BM, 10CuCe-BM, and 15CuCe-BM catalysts exhibited similar catalytic performance, suggesting that Cu in 5CuCe-BM was highly dispersed, as its activity matched that of catalysts with higher Cu content (Fig. 1c). However, excessive copper loading in the 25CuCe-BM sample led to a decrease in copper dispersion, resulting in reduced catalytic performance. Compared to 5CuCe-IWI, which was prepared via conventional impregnation, the 5CuCe-BM catalyst synthesized through mechanochemical methods demonstrated comparable catalytic performance, indicating that the mechanochemical approach is a viable alternative for industrial applications.

The apparent activation energy (E_a) values for the RWGS reaction

Fig. 1. RWGS catalytic performance. (a) CO₂ conversion and CO selectivity, (b) Arrhenius plot, and (c) Reaction activity calculated on copper metal surface area. Reaction conditions: GHSV = 30,000 mL g⁻¹ h⁻¹, H₂:CO₂:N₂ = 3:1:1, 0.1 MPa. (d) Stability test of the 5CuCe-BM and 5CuCe-IWI catalyst. Reaction conditions: GHSV = 30,000 mL g⁻¹ h⁻¹, T = 500 °C, H₂: CO₂: N₂ = 3:1:1, 0.1 MPa.

were determined from the Arrhenius plots while keeping CO₂ conversion between 5 and 20% (Fig. 1b). The *E_a* of 5CuCe-BM was approximately 57 kJ mol⁻¹, which is lower than that of other copper-cerium samples prepared by ball milling and the 5CuCe-IWI sample (63 kJ mol⁻¹) (Table 1). This is slightly lower than values reported in the literature, such as 87 kJ mol⁻¹ for 0.5CuCeO₂ and 62.8 kJ mol⁻¹ for 5CuCe. [22,29] Despite its higher dispersion, 1CuCe-BM exhibited an

Table 1
Physicochemical properties of CuCe catalysts.

Catalyst	Cu loading ^a (wt %)	D _{Cu} ^b (%)	S _{Cu} ^c (m ² g ⁻¹)	S _{BET} (m ² g ⁻¹)	<i>E_a</i> (kJ mol ⁻¹)
1CuCe-BM	0.8	100	5.2	40.0	79 ± 0.8
5CuCe-BM	3.6	91.4	21.2	69.6	57 ± 0.6
10CuCe-BM	8.4	37.0	20.0	63.2	73 ± 0.8
15CuCe-BM	13.4	24.4	21.1	43.1	82 ± 0.9
25CuCe-BM	22.3	12.3	17.7	35.8	83 ± 0.9
5CuCe-IWI	4.1	69.6	18.4	48.0	63 ± 0.7
CeO ₂ -R-BM ^d	-	-	-	81.3	-
CeO ₂ -R ^e	-	-	-	85.0	-

^a Measured by ICP-OES.

^b Cu dispersion determined by N₂O titration.

^c Cu metal surface area is based on an atomic surface density of 1.46 × 10¹⁹ Cu atoms m⁻².

^d Bare CeO₂-R after ball milling at 50 Hz for 1 h.

^e Bare CeO₂-R before ball milling.

activation energy of 78.6 kJ mol⁻¹. This higher value may be attributed to the presence of isolated Cu atoms, which do not effectively participate in redox cycles. In contrast, 5CuCe-BM likely forms small CuO_x clusters that serve as active redox sites, enhancing the catalytic cycle and lowering the reaction barrier. As Cu loading increases (≥10 wt%), *E_a* also rises due to Cu aggregation and a reduction in oxygen vacancies.

To gain further insight into the intrinsic kinetics of the catalysts, reaction orders with respect to CO₂ and H₂ were determined under differential conditions (Fig. S2). The 5CuCe-BM catalyst exhibited a CO₂ reaction order of 0.74 and an H₂ reaction order of 0.91, reflecting strong activation of both reactants on its surface. In contrast, the 5CuCe-IWI catalyst showed a CO₂ reaction order of 0.97 and an H₂ order of 0.65, indicating a relatively stronger dependence on CO₂ activation but less efficient H₂ activation. These differences highlight the more balanced and cooperative adsorption environment on 5CuCe-BM, likely due to its highly dispersed Cu and enhanced metal-support interactions.

For the long-term stability test, the performance of 5CuCe-BM and 5CuCe-IWI catalysts was compared at 500 °C over 80 h (Fig. 1d). The gradual decline in CO₂ conversion during the 80-h stability test can be attributed to reversible surface carbonation and mild sintering of Cu nanoparticles under prolonged reaction conditions. Both catalysts exhibited comparable stability; however, the ball-milled CuCe catalyst demonstrated reduced performance fluctuations in CO selectivity and CO₂ conversion. This is likely due to the mechanical forces involved in ball milling, which enhance surface area, improve copper dispersion, and create structural defects that delay sintering and generate and

stabilize additional active sites. These results suggest that CuCe-BM is a promising alternative to IWI-prepared catalysts for the RWGS process.

The lower activation energy ($E_a = 57 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$) and stable CO selectivity of 5CuCe-BM further confirm its resilient Cu-CeO₂ interface, where highly dispersed Cu sustain redox cycles more effectively than larger aggregates in 5CuCe-IWI. To further investigate the reasons for the decrease in catalyst activity, we conducted thermogravimetry analysis on 5CuCe-BM and 5CuCe-IWI after long-time stability test to detect carbon deposits (Fig. S3a). Results show the weight loss of 5CuCe-BM is 1.1% and 5.2% for 5CuCe-IWI.

Besides, Raman spectroscopy was used to characterize the catalysts after 80-h stability tests to study the formation of carbonaceous deposits (Fig. S3b). As seen in Fig. S3b, 5CuCe-IWI catalyst shows bands at ca. 1351 and 1604 cm^{-1} , which correspond to D and G bands, respectively, suggesting carbon deposition on the surface of the catalysts. Although minor carbonate deposition cannot be ruled out, the absence of significant coke formation on 5CuCe-BM and negligible Cu particle growth (Fig. 2 and Fig. S3) underscores the robustness of the ball-milled catalyst. These insights highlight the trade-off between Cu loading and dispersion, with 5CuCe-BM striking an optimal balance for long-term RWGS performance.

3.2. Catalyst characterization

The physicochemical properties of the xCuCe-BM catalysts and the reference 5CuCe-IWI are summarized in Table 1. The 5CuCe-BM catalyst exhibits the highest BET surface area ($69.6 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$) among the xCuCe-BM catalysts and significantly exceeds that of 5CuCe-IWI ($48.0 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$) (Table 1 and Fig. S4). As the copper content increases in xCuCe-BM, Cu dispersion (D_{Cu}) gradually decreases. Conversely, the Cu metal surface area (S_{Cu}) shows no obvious change with increasing copper content, reaching $21.2 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ for 5CuCe-BM, $20.0 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ for 10CuCe-BM, and $21.1 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ for 15CuCe-BM, suggesting that 5CuCe-BM provides an adequate number of Cu active sites for the RWGS reaction. When Cu content increased to 25%, the Cu metal surface area (S_{Cu}) decreased to $12.3 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$, explaining the observed decline in catalytic performance due to severe Cu agglomeration. Compared to 5CuCe-BM, which exhibits a high Cu dispersion of approximately 91.4%, 5CuCe-IWI shows a lower Cu dispersion (69.6%) and, consequently, a reduced Cu metal surface area ($18.4 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$).

To further investigate the morphology and nanostructure of the catalysts, HAADF-STEM-EDX analyses were conducted. The catalysts consist of irregularly shaped crystallites with an average size of $5 \pm 1 \text{ nm}$ (Fig. S5a). Fig. 2 shows a representative image of the sample 5CuCe-BM

after reduction. EDX elemental mapping reveals that Ce and O are uniformly distributed, while Cu is both uniformly highly dispersed and partially aggregated into clusters (Fig. 2 and Fig. S5c).

The dispersion of Cu species in 5CuCe-BM was further investigated by DRIFTS measurements using CO as a probe molecule (Fig. S6). Upon CO adsorption, a strong peak at 2118 cm^{-1} appeared, attributed to CO* adsorbed on isolated Cu⁺ ions at the CeO₂ interface. Additionally, a small shoulder peak at 2163 cm^{-1} was observed, corresponding to CO* adsorbed on defective Cu⁰ sites. With increased purging time, both peaks remained even after the gaseous CO signals disappeared, and their positions showed negligible shifts, as indirect evidence of high dispersion of Cu species.

Crystal structure analysis confirmed the ceria fluorite structure, with lattice spacings of 0.340 nm for the (111) plane, 0.219 nm for the (022) plane and 0.283 nm for the (200) plane (Fig. 2 and Fig. S5b). The presence of sub-nano Cu was also identified, with a lattice spacing of 0.214 nm corresponding to the (111) plane. As expected, ball milling disrupted the CeO₂ nanorod structure but allowed the incorporation of Cu into the Ce lattice, potentially leading to a higher density of oxygen vacancies. [40,41] This process caused the expansion of the CeO₂ (111), (022) and (200) planes beyond the conventional values of 0.271 nm for the (200) plane, 0.191 nm for the (022) plane and 0.312 nm for the (111) plane, which potentially promotes CO₂ activation. [40] After an 80-h reaction time, HAADF-STEM analysis of 5CuCe-BM (Fig. S7) revealed a slight sintering of both the ceria support and Cu. In contrast, EDX mapping of 5CuCe-IWI after H₂ pretreatment (Fig. 3) revealed the presence of larger copper nanoparticles, underscoring the critical role of the ball milling method in enhancing Cu dispersion.

The XRD patterns of the CuCe-BM catalysts with varying Cu content show distinct diffraction peaks at 28.6° , 33.1° , 47.5° , and 56.3° , corresponding to the (111), (200), (220), and (311) planes of the fluorite cubic CeO₂ phase (Fig. 4a). Additionally, peaks at 35.5° , 38.7° , and 48.8° , assigned to the monoclinic CuO phase, gradually emerge with increasing Cu content above 10%. No crystalline CuO phases are observed in 1CuCe-BM, 5CuCe-BM and 5CuCe-IWI samples, likely due to the small amount of Cu and its notable dispersion. After reducing the xCuCe-BM catalysts in 10% H₂/Ar at 600 °C, the samples exhibit minimal structural changes in the ceria phase. Before H₂ reduction, the average lattice constant of the copper-ceria samples was smaller than that of CeO₂, as estimated from the CeO₂ (311) reflection using the Bragg and Debye-Scherrer equations (Table S1). This lattice contraction suggests the partial incorporation of Cu²⁺ ions into the CeO₂ lattice due to their smaller ionic radius compared to Ce⁴⁺. However, after reduction, the average lattice constant increased (Table S1), likely due to

Fig. 2. HAADF-STEM image and corresponding EDX elemental maps of 5CuCe-BM catalyst with H₂ pretreatment.

Fig. 3. HAADF-STEM image and corresponding EDX elemental maps of 5CuCe-IWI catalyst with H₂ pretreatment.

Fig. 4. (a,b) XRD patterns of the fresh (a) and 10% H₂/Ar pretreatment (b) xCuCe-BM and xCuCe-IWI catalysts. (c,d) Raman spectra of fresh (c) and 10% H₂/Ar pretreatment (d) xCuCe-BM catalysts.

thermal expansion caused by the partial migration of Cu out of the CeO₂ lattice. Peaks at 43.3° and 50.5° correspond to the (111) and (200) planes of cubic metallic Cu (Fig. 4b). In 5CuCe-IWI, a peak corresponding to metallic Cu is detected after reduction (Fig. 4b and Fig. S8). In contrast, in 1CuCe-BM and 5CuCe-BM, no characteristic peaks for metallic Cu are observed, indicating that Cu species remain stable on CeO₂ without agglomeration, even under high-temperature reduction.

The XRD pattern of the 5CuCe-BM after an 80-h stability test was also analyzed to assess structural changes following the RWGS reaction (Fig. S8). A peak of metallic Cu is hardly visible, which suggests a strong interaction between CeO₂ and atomically dispersed Cu and/or small Cu clusters.

The intensity of the metallic Cu XRD peak in 5CuCe-BM samples processed at varying ball-milling frequencies and durations was

relatively strong (Fig. S9), implying the presence of larger Cu particles on CeO₂ and a correspondingly lower catalytic performance (Fig. S1). Among the tested samples, 5CuCe-BM processed at 50 Hz for 60 min exhibited the highest catalytic performance. This superior performance is correlated with the absence of a noticeable metallic Cu peak in the XRD pattern, suggesting a finer dispersion of Cu species on CeO₂. In contrast, the 5CuCe-BM sample processed at 50 Hz for only 10 min and the sample processed at 15 Hz for 60 min exhibited distinct metallic Cu peaks, indicating insufficient dispersion and the formation of larger Cu particles. The lower milling frequency (15 Hz) likely resulted in reduced impact energy, limiting Cu particle refinement, while the shorter milling duration (10 min) at 50 Hz may not have allowed sufficient time for effective particle size reduction and uniform dispersion. Therefore, the combination of a high milling frequency (50 Hz) and an extended duration (60 min) was the most effective in optimizing the catalyst structure and enhancing its performance.

The Raman spectra of the fresh CuCe-BM catalysts exhibit distinct peaks at about 254, 462, and 600 cm⁻¹, corresponding to the CeO₂ second-order transverse acoustic mode (2TA), the lattice mode (F_{2g}), and the defect-induced mode (D), respectively (Fig. 4c). The band at 600 cm⁻¹ consists of two components, one at approximately 550 cm⁻¹

and the other at 615 cm⁻¹. The component at 550 cm⁻¹ arises from defects that include oxygen vacancies with a symmetry different from that of the O_h point group, while the component at 615 cm⁻¹ corresponds to defects without oxygen vacancies that retain O_h symmetry. [42] As copper content increases, the intensity of the D band initially rises and then decreases, indicating a higher defect concentration in 5CuCe-BM compared to the other Cu-doped catalysts. No distinct peaks associated with CuO are observed, likely because CuO does not form large surface aggregates but instead appears as atomically dispersed Cu or CuO clusters, which is in accordance with the HAADF-STEM-EDX and XRD results discussed above. Overall, the Raman spectroscopy results corroborate the Cu incorporation into the CeO₂ lattice.

The intensity ratio of the D band to the F_{2g} band (I_D/I_{F2g}) was calculated to assess the concentration of defects in the CuCe-BM catalysts (Fig. S10). After H₂ reduction, a significant increase in the I_D/I_{F2g} value was observed compared to fresh catalysts, indicating that the reduction process is critical for defects formation (Fig. 4d). Additionally, the F_{2g} band of the CuCe-BM catalysts broadened and exhibited a redshift after H₂ pretreatment (Fig. S11). These changes are attributed to Ce⁴⁺ reduction to Ce³⁺ on the CeO₂ surface via hydrogen spillover, which affects the vibrational properties of the CeO₂ lattice, enhances the

Fig. 5. (a) Deconvoluted H₂-TPR profiles of temperature for the low-temperature reduction zone and (b) CO₂-TPD profiles of CuCe-BM and CuCe-IWI catalysts.

concentration of oxygen vacancies and increases the concentration of surface defects. In contrast, the I_D/I_{2g} of bare CeO₂ and 5CuCe-IWI after H₂ reduction decreased (Figs. S10 and S12). For CeO₂, this is likely due to the facilitation of defect healing, oxygen vacancy migration, and recombination during H₂ reduction at high temperatures, leading to a decrease in defects. However, compared to 5CuCe-BM, for 5CuCe-IWI, the weak Cu-CeO₂ interaction allows Cu to detach from the CeO₂ lattice and sinter during high-temperature reduction, resulting in Cu coalescence on the CeO₂ surface and a consequent reduction in detectable surface defects.

To investigate the interaction between highly dispersed Cu and CeO₂ in the RWGS reaction, we conducted H₂-TPR experiments (Fig. 5a). A weak hydrogen consumption signal was observed in the high-temperature region (above 600 °C) for all CuCe-BM catalysts, indicating the reduction of bulk CeO₂ (Fig. S13c). Deconvolution of the TPR profiles in the low-temperature region (50–300 °C, Table S2) revealed four distinct peaks, each corresponding to different copper–oxygen entities over the supported copper oxide catalysts reduced by H₂: (I) isolated copper oxide species; (II) sub-nm CuO_x clusters; (III) small two- or three-dimensional CuO clusters with structures so loose that they have no specific and regular lattice array; (IV) bulk CuO with properties and characteristics similar with those of pure CuO powders. The TPR profile of pure CuO (Fig. S13a) exhibited an asymmetrical peak centered at 249 °C, characteristic of the stepwise reduction of CuO through Cu⁺ to Cu⁰ states. Compared to pure CuO, the high dispersion of copper in CuCe-BM catalysts significantly lowered the reduction temperature, suggesting that the α and β peaks represent the progressive reduction of CuO_x species or clusters to Cu⁺ and Cu⁰ states rather than a single reducible species. The high-temperature γ peak (above 200 °C) was associated with the reduction of the bulk or large CuO nanoparticles. In the case of 1CuCe-BM, only sub-200 °C peaks were attributed to atomic dispersion (Cu⁺/small clusters) with strong CeO₂ interaction. With increasing Cu content (>10 wt%), a peak over 210 °C is observed, corresponding to Cu aggregation to form bulk CuO or nanoparticles. For the 5CuCe-IWI catalyst, there are four reduction peaks (labeled I, II, III and IV), which can be assigned to the reduction of the isolated copper oxide species, sub-nm CuO_x clusters, small two- or three-dimensional CuO clusters and large CuO particles, respectively. These results confirm that ball milling is an excellent method for preparing highly dispersed copper-ceria catalysts.

Notably, the actual H₂ consumption in the TPR profiles of Cu-CeO₂ catalysts exceeded the theoretical amount required for complete Cu²⁺ to Cu⁰ reduction (Table S2), indicating a strong interaction between highly dispersed Cu and CeO₂. To better understand the contributions of each component, both Cu-only and total H₂ consumption values were calculated and compared. The Cu-only consumption reflects the reduction behavior and dispersion state of Cu species, while the total H₂ uptake includes additional reduction of CeO₂ (Ce⁴⁺ to Ce³⁺) and possible surface oxygen removal. For example, the CeO₂-BM sample showed a theoretical H₂ consumption of 0.29 mmol g⁻¹, while the experimental value was 0.49 mmol g⁻¹, indicating partial Ce⁴⁺ reduction and potential involvement of surface oxygen species. The excess H₂ consumption observed provides indirect but valuable evidence that the surface oxygen bound to the ceria nanorods can also be reduced by the aids of highly dispersed Cu at low temperatures (<300 °C), which has been observed previously and may enhance the catalytic activity through improved oxygen mobility and hydrogen activation.

The adsorption of CO₂ on the catalysts was assessed by CO₂-TPD. CO₂ adsorption regions are divided into three main sections (Fig. 5b): weak (< 200 °C), medium (200–500 °C), and strong (> 500 °C) adsorption. For catalysts prepared via ball milling, no distinct peaks but broad desorption in the 200–800 °C range were observed which could result from the structural heterogeneity and diversity of basic sites induced by the mechanochemical treatment. To semi-quantitatively compare the distribution of basic sites, the CO₂-TPD profiles were divided into three temperature regions, and the desorption areas were calculated by

numerical integration (Fig. 5b). This approach avoids peak-fitting errors associated with the deconvolution of broad or overlapped signals. The low-temperature region (α , 50–200 °C) corresponds to weak CO₂ adsorption sites associated with surface hydroxyl groups of the support, leading to the formation of thermally unstable bicarbonate species. Compared to the number of basic sites on the bare CeO₂ support (Fig. S14), the addition of copper enhances CO₂ adsorption, except in the case of 5CuCe-IWI. As the copper content increases, there is an initial slight decrease in weak basic sites, followed by a significant increase (Table S3). Medium basic sites (β , 200–500 °C) represent intermediate-strength Lewis basic sites, typically related to surface O²⁻ species, oxygen vacancies adjacent to Ce⁴⁺/Ce³⁺ redox pairs, and Cu⁰-O-Ce⁴⁺ interfacial structures. [43] As shown in Table S3, the number of medium basic sites increases from 74 $\mu\text{mol g}_{\text{cat}}^{-1}$ (1CuCe-BM) to 176 $\mu\text{mol g}_{\text{cat}}^{-1}$ (10CuCe-BM) before decreasing to 103 $\mu\text{mol g}_{\text{cat}}^{-1}$ (15CuCe-BM) and further to 124 $\mu\text{mol g}_{\text{cat}}^{-1}$ (25CuCe-BM). This suggests that surface Cu species in nanoscale or cluster form likely contribute to intermediate CO₂ adsorption and enhance the metal-support interaction between Cu and CeO₂.

For catalysts prepared via ball milling, no sharp peaks are observed in the medium and strong basic regions, indicating that highly dispersed Cu exposes more surface-active sites. [36] While previous reports have indicated that, in the RWGS reaction, medium-strength basic sites are generally favored for optimal performance since excessively strong basic sites can lead to over-adsorption of CO₂ and hinder the reaction—the ball-milled catalysts demonstrate a unique synergy. [44] These sites facilitate effective CO₂ adsorption and activation, striking a balance between binding strength and reactivity. Strong basic sites (γ , 500–800 °C) possibly correspond to CO₂ strongly adsorbed on bulk lattice oxygen, deeply embedded oxygen vacancies, or stable Cu⁺-O-Ce³⁺ structural motifs. These features contribute to robust metal–support interactions, mitigate sintering, and help preserve active sites under reaction conditions. For CO₂ adsorption over 5CuCe-IWI, the weak and medium adsorption abilities are similar to those of 5CuCe-BM, likely reflecting comparable catalytic performance. Compared to 5CuCe-BM (133 $\mu\text{mol g}_{\text{cat}}^{-1}$) and bare CeO₂ (103 $\mu\text{mol g}_{\text{cat}}^{-1}$), the strong basic sites in 5CuCe-IWI exhibit significantly reduced CO₂ adsorption (23 $\mu\text{mol g}_{\text{cat}}^{-1}$), indicating that the IWI method limits the ability to sustain the CO₂ activation-desorption cycle. This may explain the fluctuations in CO₂ conversion and CO selectivity observed during the 80-h stability test. In contrast, the ball milling process generates interconnected β - and γ -sites, enabling the spillover of activated CO₂ from γ - to β -sites for subsequent reduction, thereby alleviating issues related to over-adsorption.

The Ce and O surface chemical states of the reduced catalysts were examined using XPS (Figs. 6 and S16). The Ce 3d XPS spectra consist of two sets of spin-orbital multiplets (Fig. 6a). The peaks labeled v⁰ (880.5 eV), v (882.5 eV), v' (884.3 eV), v'' (889.0 eV) and v''' (898.4 eV) are attributed to Ce 3d_{5/2}, while those labeled u⁰ (899.1 eV), u (901.1 eV), u' (902.9 eV), u'' (907.6 eV) and u''' (917 eV) belong to Ce 3d_{3/2}. The peaks v⁰, v', u⁰, and u' are ascribed to Ce³⁺ while the remaining six peaks are assigned to Ce⁴⁺ species. The surface concentration of Ce³⁺ was calculated via the ratio of Ce³⁺/(Ce³⁺+Ce⁴⁺), which is related to the surface oxygen vacancies caused by the reduction of Ce⁴⁺. Table S4 presents the concentration of Ce³⁺ species in different catalysts. As expected, H₂ pretreatment induces the formation of oxygen vacancies in the catalyst structure, and the surface concentration of Ce³⁺ of 5CuCe-BM-cal increases from 0.17 to 0.19 after reduction. This value is higher than that of the 5CuCe-IWI catalyst, which suggests that the preparation of the copper-ceria catalysts by ball milling facilitates the formation of oxygen vacancies. Even after the long-time stability test, the surface concentration of Ce³⁺ remains at 0.22. The O 1s XPS spectra reveal three peaks (Fig. 6b). The main peak (O_w) at 529.8 eV is assigned to lattice oxygen, the peak (O _{β}) at 531.9 eV corresponds to adsorbed surface oxygen species at surface oxygen vacancies, and the peak (O _{γ}) at 532.7 eV is associated with weakly bound surface oxygen species. The ratio of O _{β} /(O _{α} + O _{β} + O _{γ}) can be indicative of the density of surface oxygen

Fig. 6. High-resolution (a) Ce 3d and (b) O 1s XPS spectra of fresh 5CuCe-BM, 5CuCe-BM after H₂ reduction and 5CuCe-BM after long-time stability test.

vacancies. As shown in Table S4, the concentration of O_p was 0.14 on the fresh 5CuCe-BM catalyst, slightly increasing to 0.29 after H₂ reduction, and then to 0.31 on the 5CuCe-BM after the reaction, which can be attributed to the structural reconstruction of CeO₂. During the long-time stability test, the catalyst undergoes repeated redox cycles. Prolonged operation may induce surface restructuring, exposing more defective CeO₂ interfaces where oxygen vacancies preferentially form. The synergy between Cu and CeO₂ enhances oxygen mobility, further promoting vacancy formation. Over time, Ce³⁺ species are stabilized, as indicated by the similarity in the Ce³⁺/(Ce³⁺ + Ce⁴⁺) ratio. This suggests a partial reduction of Ce⁴⁺ to Ce³⁺, which maintains the oxygen vacancies. To further confirm the presence of oxygen vacancies in the CuCe-BM and 5CuCe-IWI catalysts, EPR spectroscopy was conducted, and the results are presented in Fig. S18. All EPR signals are symmetric with g-values of 2.004, indicating the presence of unpaired electrons associated with oxygen vacancies. The signal intensities reflect the relative densities of oxygen vacancies in the following order: 5CuCe-BM > 10CuCe-BM > 5CuCe-IWI > 15CuCe-BM > 25CuCe-BM > 1CuCe-BM. This trend is consistent with the results obtained from XPS results and the Raman D/F_{2g} ratios.

XPS and Auger analyses (Fig. S17) revealed the evolution of copper species in Cu/CeO₂ catalysts. The fresh 5CuCe-BM sample exhibits Cu 2p_{3/2} binding energies at 933.4 eV and 934.7 eV with weak satellite features, along with LMM Auger peaks at 914.9 eV and 917.1 eV, yielding Auger parameters (α') (BE+KE) of 1848.3 eV and 1851.8 eV, respectively. These values suggest the presence of Cu⁺ species, rather than exclusively Cu²⁺. After H₂ reduction, the Cu 2p_{3/2} peak shifts to 932.7 eV (indicative of Cu^{+/Cu}), with the disappearance of satellite features, and Cu LM2 shows peaks at 916.4 eV and 918.8 eV, confirming the dominance of Cu⁺ stabilized by oxygen vacancies. When combined with XRD, CO₂-TPD, and HRREM-EDX results, these findings indicate the formation of highly dispersed Cu⁺ species strongly interacting with CeO₂. In contrast, 5CuCe-IWI exhibits a reduced Cu⁺ content and a higher proportion of Cu⁰ (Table S4). The spent 5CuCe-BM sample maintains a Cu⁺-dominant state (932.7 eV, α' = 1854.5 eV), indicating good electronic stability.

The XPS-derived Cu/Ce surface molar ratios reveal remarkably consistent Cu distribution across ball-milled catalysts, with 5CuCe-BM showing minimal variation before (0.114) and after H₂ treatment

(0.117) (Table S4). This contrasts with the impregnated sample (0.136), where significant surface Cu enrichment occurs. 5CuCe-BM-post (0.129) shows excellent structural stability, correlating with the catalyst's sustained performance. This homogeneous Cu dispersion creates abundant Cu⁺-O-Ce³⁺ interfaces that are crucial for CO₂ activation while suppressing Cu nanoparticle sintering. The near-constant ratios in ball-milled samples, coupled with the observed CeO₂ lattice contraction (Table S1), strongly suggest partial Cu²⁺ incorporation into the ceria lattice as isolated ions. These results underscore the advantage of mechanochemical synthesis in stabilizing Cu⁺ species through strong metal-support interactions and enhanced resistance to sintering.

3.3. In situ DRIFTS

To investigate the evolution of intermediate species over catalysts with varying copper content, in situ DRIFTS spectra were obtained for the RWGS reaction (Fig. 7 and Fig. S19). For all catalysts, a peak at 2173 cm⁻¹, corresponding to the linear adsorption of CO on isolated Cu⁺ sites, is observed as the temperature increases to 300 °C. A peak at approximately 2120 cm⁻¹, attributed to the linear adsorption of CO on highly dispersed Cu⁰, is present in all catalysts except 1CuCe-BM, indicating the absence of Cu⁰ in this sample and suggesting limited H₂ dissociation capacity for RWGS reaction. Additionally, an extra peak at 2080 cm⁻¹ appears for 25CuCe-BM, associated with small, unsaturated Cu⁰ clusters, whereas a peak at 1980 cm⁻¹ is observed for 5CuCe-IWI, corresponding to larger Cu⁰ particles. These findings demonstrate the effectiveness of ball milling in producing highly dispersed copper catalysts. For the 1CuCe-BM, 5CuCe-BM, 25CuCe-BM and 5CuCe-IWI catalysts, exposure to CO₂ and H₂ at room temperature resulted in the formation of monodentate bicarbonate species (approximately at 1618, 1438, and 1213 cm⁻¹) and few bidentate carbonate species (1564, and 1310 cm⁻¹), with bicarbonate species predominantly observed on the 1CuCe-BM and 5CuCe-BM catalyst. For 1CuCe-BM, the intensity of bicarbonate peaks gradually increased as the temperature increased to 300 °C, accompanied by the emergence of new peaks at 2949, 2848, 1369 and 1075 cm⁻¹. The peak at 2951 cm⁻¹ corresponds to the C—H stretching vibration of formate species, while the peak at 1369 cm⁻¹ is attributed to the symmetric O-C-O stretching vibration of formate species (denoted as *HCOO). The asymmetric O-C-O stretching vibration of formate species

Fig. 7. In situ DRIFTS spectra of the RWGS process over reduced (a) 1CuCe-BM, (b) 5CuCe-BM and (c) 25CuCe-BM catalysts. Reduction conditions: 600 °C for 1 h in 10% H₂/Ar (40 mL min⁻¹). Reaction conditions: CO₂/H₂/Ar = 5/15/20 (40 mL min⁻¹), 0.1 MPa.

was overlapped by bidentate carbonate. Simultaneously, bands at 1075 cm⁻¹ progressively increased and were assigned to the C—O bond stretching vibration in methoxy species (*H₃CO), while the feature at 2848 cm⁻¹ corresponded to the symmetric vibration of the C—H bond in methoxy species. When temperature continues to increase, the signal formate and methoxy species gradually disappear indicating an increase in the reaction rate. For 5CuCe-BM, the amount of formate and methoxy species was higher during the RWGS reaction compared to 1CuCe-BM and 25CuCe-BM. It is worth mentioning that the 5CuCe catalyst prepared by the IWI method also shows the signal of formate and methoxy species (Fig. S19). However, 5CuCe-IWI has weaker formate and methoxy intensity than 5CuCe-BM, suggesting that the ball-milling method produces a more highly dispersed and active copper phase. Conversely, almost no signals of formate and methoxy species were detected for 25CuCe-BM. Moreover, the 1407 cm⁻¹ peak (bridged carbonate/formate at Cu-CeO₂ interfaces) appears exclusively in ball-milled catalysts, with intensity scaling as 5CuCe-BM > 25CuCe-BM > 1CuCe-BM. This trend reflects ball milling's ability to generate defective interfaces that stabilize cooperative CO₂ adsorption where a feature absent in IWI-prepared catalysts. The 1407 cm⁻¹ signal thus serves as a direct spectroscopic proxy for the interfacial synergy critical to RWGS activity. This observation indicates that highly dispersed copper

promotes CO₂ adsorption and facilitates the RWGS reaction.

In situ DRIFT spectra were further recorded to monitor intermediates and catalytic processes during the RWGS reaction at low temperatures (350 °C, Fig. 8 and Fig. S20). When a mixed flow of H₂ and CO₂ was first introduced at this temperature, significant signals for formate intermediates (*HCOO, at approximately 2947, 2841, 1565, and 1365 cm⁻¹) were observed on the 1CuCe-BM, 5CuCe-BM, and 25CuCe-BM catalysts (Fig. 8). Additionally, signals corresponding to methoxy species (*H₃CO, at approximately 2925, 2808, and 1078 cm⁻¹) were detected on 1CuCe-BM, but not on 5CuCe-BM and 25CuCe-BM. Subsequently, the H₂ flow was stopped, and the catalysts were treated with only CO₂ at 350 °C, ceasing the production of activated H species. The characteristic peaks for *HCOO intermediates significantly decreased during CO₂ exposure. Moreover, *H₃CO intermediates on 5CuCe-BM and 25CuCe-BM disappeared quickly, while no notable change was observed on 1CuCe-BM. This suggests that the abundant strong basic sites on 1CuCe-BM facilitate *HCOO desorption and continued hydrogenation. Notably, with increasing copper loading, the intensity of *HCOO and *H₃CO intermediates decreased (Fig. S21). This result implies that highly dispersed copper and higher copper content enhance H₂ affinity, leading to reduced accumulation of *HCOO on the catalyst surface. Then, there is a delicate equilibrium between Cu loading and Cu

Fig. 8. In situ DRIFTS spectra of RWGS process over reduced (a) 1CuCe-BM, (b) 5CuCe-BM and (c) 25CuCe-BM catalysts. Reduction conditions: 600 °C for 1 h in 10% H₂/Ar (40 mL min⁻¹). Reaction conditions: CO₂/H₂/Ar = 5/15/20 (40 mL min⁻¹), 0.1 MPa, 350 °C.

dispersion leading to optimum catalytic performance, which is found in the 5CuCe-BM catalyst. The intermediate species evolution of samples 5CuCe-BM and 5CuCe-IWI is very similar (Fig. S21).

4. Conclusions

In summary, Cu-CeO₂ catalysts with highly dispersed copper sites were successfully fabricated via mechanochemistry, significantly enhancing catalytic activity for the RWGS reaction. The systematic variation of Cu loading allowed the investigation of the influence of Cu-support interactions on the RWGS reaction. Notably, the optimal 5CuCe-BM catalyst demonstrated excellent reaction activity ($R_{\text{Cu}}(\text{CO}_2)$) of $4.8 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol}_{\text{CO}_2} \text{ m}_{\text{Cu}}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 450 °C, achieving nearly 100% selectivity. The strong copper-ceria interaction remained intact after activation under hydrogen and RWGS reaction due to the high-energy ball milling process. The outstanding catalytic performance is attributed to the high dispersion of copper, as confirmed by microscopy and spectroscopic analyses. The increased dispersion of copper enhances CO₂ adsorption and activation, while simultaneously facilitating H₂ dissociation at the

copper sites, which are critical to the catalytic process. DRIFTS results further revealed that the RWGS reaction over CuCe-BM catalysts proceeds via the formate pathway, independent of copper content. Overall, this study provides an efficient and effective method for fabricating CuCe catalysts with high copper dispersion for the RWGS reaction.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Xuan Lu: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Jing Yu:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Junshan Li:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization. **Isabel Serrano:** Resources, Investigation, Data curation. **Jordi Arbiol:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Andreu Cabot:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Jordi Llorca:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2025.165039>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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